

Transthyretin alters cardiac fibroblast structure, function and inflammatory gene expression.

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Supplementary Information

Supplementary Movie S1: Cardiac fibroblasts plated on fibronectin only (UT) and live imaged for 6 hours. (Separate file attached)

Supplementary Movie S2: Cardiac fibroblasts plated on fibronectin plus TTR fibrils (TTR) and live imaged for 6 hours. (Separate file attached)

Supplementary Figure S3:

Supplementary Figure S3. Functional enrichment analysis of differentially expressed terms show over-representation of many immune response terms and pathways. (A) Functional enrichment analysis in g:Profiler reveals over-represented terms and pathways in Gene Ontology: Molecular Function (GO:MF), Gene Ontology: Biological Processes (GO:BP), KEGG Pathways (KEGG), and Reactome Pathways (REAC). A full, interactive version of this plot can be found at <https://tinyurl.com/UICTTR>. **(B)** Enriched Gene Ontology: Molecular Function (GO:MF) terms for differentially expressed genes, selected by largest fraction of differentially expressed genes associated with each term. **(C)** Enriched Reactome pathways for differentially expressed genes selected by largest fraction of differentially expressed genes associated with each pathway. (n = 3 biological replicates per condition, normalized by trimmed-mean of M-values scaling in edgeR, FDR-adjusted P < 0.05)

Supplementary Figure S4:

Supplementary Figure S4. Normalized Log₂ counts per million of differentially expressed genes for each biological replicate, hierarchically clustered on the basis of Euclidean distance.

Supplementary Table S5: RNAseq differential analysis. (Separate file attached)

Supplementary Table S6: RNAseq Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA). (Separate file attached)

Supplementary Methods:

Bioinformatic analysis of RNA-Seq data is as follows. Raw reads were aligned to the rat reference genome (rn6) in a splice-aware manner using the STAR aligner(2). Expression level of ENSEMBL genes was quantified using FeatureCounts (5). Differential expression statistics were computed using edgeR(6), and p-values were adjusted for multiple testing using the false discovery rate correction of Benjamini and Hochberg. Pathway analysis of differentially expressed genes was performed in Ingenuity Pathway Analysis.

Transcriptomic data was visualized in RStudio (Rstudio, Boston, MA). Differential expression and statistical significance were visualized through volcano plots created using EnhancedVolcano(1). Normalized log₂ counts per million of differentially expressed genes of individual samples were plotted on a heatmap using Pheatmap(4). Functional enrichment analysis was conducted using gProfiler2(3), clusterProfiler(9), and ReactomePA(8). Subsequent visualization of specific database terms were plotted using Enrichplot (7).

Supplementary References:

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